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USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of using new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of English, and analyzes all the possibilities of the student, taking into account the complexity of learning the subject. Also, examples of new methods in language development are given and its importance is revealed. At the same time, ways of improving the quality of education by using innovative methods of the English language teacher of general secondary schools are highlighted.*

Key words: *qualities of creativity, knowledge, skills, qualifications, creative activity, personality creativity, professional creativity.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается важность использования новых педагогических технологий в преподавании английского языка, анализируются все возможности студента с учетом сложности изучения предмета. Также приводятся примеры новых методов в развитии речи и раскрывается их важность. При этом выделены пути повышения качества образования за счет использования инновационных методов работы учителя английского языка общеобразовательных школ.*

Ключевые слова: *качества креативности, знания, умения, квалификация, творческая активность, личностная креативность, профессиональная креативность.*

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ingliz tili fanini o'qitishda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati xususida soz yuritilar ekan, fanni o'zlashtirish biroz murakkabligini hisobga olgan holda o'quvchining barcha imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek tilni rivojlantirishda yangi metodlardan misollar keltirilib, uning ahamiyati ochib beriladi. Hamda, umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari ingliz tili o'qituvchisining innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish yo'llari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kreativlik sifatlari, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, ijodiy faoliyat, shaxs kreativligi, kasbiy ijodkorlik.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. A number of English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will definitely increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. Teaching using technology has several unique advantages. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward. Technology is slowly replacing traditional teaching. Today, a number of new programs and shows that help to teach English are regularly broadcast on television programs. It should also be noted that today new methods of using modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan to increase the effectiveness of teaching. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of multimedia has the opportunity to develop four skills and learn both by seeing and hearing through interesting materials. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it. Of course, the use of modern technologies such as computers, radios, CDs, and DVDs in any foreign language classes will advance the educational process and allow the young generation to learn foreign languages faster. The fact that

some teachers do not know how to retain and use technologies during English classes, leads to some boredom of students.¹

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this reason, the use of technologies and at least the computer during the lesson will ensure that the interest of the participant increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the age, interest, ability, and learning of the students will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we, the teachers, do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, spoons, or texts consisting of complex words to elementary school students, or show them through multimedia, computers, or if we show educational materials consisting of very simple texts to middle and upper classes or group organizers. teachers' interest in language learning gradually fades and they stop teaching. This, in turn, can lead to a decrease in grades and the loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students. Therefore, it follows that the main task is not only to use technologies during the lesson, but also to keep them to a minimum and to ensure that the use of technologies serves to improve the student's knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. the International European Education Standards, it is important to use technologies efficiently and effectively during the lessons on the competencies of writing, reading, listening, speaking in English. For example, in listening comprehension lessons, there are also rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the participant to understand the audio material he is listening to and to be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare the environment for broadcasting the audio material, in which the listeners should provide a peaceful environment, and the teacher should pay attention to the quality of the audio being played and the sound amplifiers are working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio broadcasting should be ready and

¹ Bekmuratova U. B. "Ingliz tilini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish" mavzusida referat. Toshkent — 2012 yil
Орабоева, М. Р. Чет тилини о'қитишда замонавий инноватсион технологияларидан фойдаланиш ва унинг самарадорлиги.

the organizers should be provided with handouts. . After all the requirements are fulfilled, the teacher can start broadcasting the audio material to the organizers. Listening is done at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material. It is also a very effective way to show and discuss videos, movies, and videos to the participants using multimedia in the process of teaching using technology while adjusting and recording. It is possible to use a vocabulary familiar to the participants, comment on the words if new and complex words are involved, and show the video material after completing the exercises related to the new words. In order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of watching for everyone, and checking that the sound amplifiers are working. Before uploading the video, the organizers should talk about the topic of the video to be shown, ask questions, and after making sure that the students are really interested in this topic, upload the video material. When the video is over, the teacher should be interested in the students' thoughts about the video and perform exercises. After these steps are completed, these lessons will definitely contribute to the growth of interest and knowledge of the organisers.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

After these steps are completed, these lessons will definitely contribute to the growth of interest and knowledge of the organisers. It follows from this that the role of modern technologies in enriching our lessons, interesting the teachers, and enriching their knowledge is incomparable. Being able to keep them right and correct is the main guarantee of our success. After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community today, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation

with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these thoughts, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European framework for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, among other things: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; - it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio

broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which allows students to demonstrate their abilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this exercise than in a regular lesson and works freely.¹

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to educate mature professionals who have a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, and the ability to solve their tasks without difficulty, today our pedagogic teachers use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies. They should understand that it is the main factor of increasing the quality and efficiency of education, and that it is required by the times. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can play English games, speak, listen, understand, and write, and he is interested. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be a subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently.

¹ .PQ 1875 “Chet tillarni organish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari togrisida” gi qaror. “ Xalq sozi” gazetasi, 2-bet. 2012 yil,10-dekabr

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